

Data Management Plan for Academy of Finland

Title of proposal: Early-life stress and psychiatric disorders: Role of the stress axis on the development of the serotonergic system in depression and anxiety disorders

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Description: This project will investigate the effect of birth asphyxia as a risk factor for mental disorders on the functional development of the serotonergic system in an animal model. Using most electrophysiological measurements, I will address if birth asphyxia increases the firing activity of serotonergic neurons and alters how serotonin release is controlled. I will test if this is mediated by the activation of the stress axis by birth asphyxia and the resulting hyperelevated levels of the stress hormone arginine vasopressin. Finally, I will explore if birth asphyxia alters long-range interactions in the developing brain and if these could be mediated by altered serotonergic tone. The data I will collect are mostly time series of brain activity in vitro and in vivo which will generate large volumes of data. I will analyse these with appropriate methods to answer the questions as mentioned above.

1. COLLABORATORS (ARCHIVES, STORAGE SERVICES, ETC.)

With which collaborators will the data be managed and made openly available?

The research data from this project will be deposited on two Dell PowerEdge R515 storage servers housed by the University of Helsinki IT services. Each server has 40 TB of disk space in a RAID6 configuration resulting in ~30 TB of effective storage space and fault tolerance for two simultaneous drive failures. One of the servers acts as the primary data store, while the other mirrors the primary. Both servers can be upgraded for additional storage space should it be needed.

I chose this partner since similar types of data from my collaborator Prof. K. Kaila have been successfully stored there and I could use this server without further extra costs.

2. TYPE OF DATA

What types of data (e.g. qualitative, quantitative, measurements) will the project collect or use? The data content is described in more detail in the research plan.

The data will consist of laboratory notebooks, large volumes of raw time series data files as collected by electrophysiological or electrochemical recordings in the brain (see detailed description in the research plan), experimental analysis files as generated in Matlab, Excel, SPSS or Graphpad Prism, microscopy images and video files of the behavioural experiments.

3. TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

How will the data be documented? For example, what file format and metadata standard will be used?

The in vivo electrophysiological data will be in the .ncs format that can be easily imported into analysis programs such as Matlab or Spike2. The in vitro electrophysiological data will be in .dat or .edr format and can be viewed and analysed with several programs including WinEDR, Clampfit or Matlab after file conversion to .abf. The in vitro FCV data will be in the .wcp format (Strathclyde Whole Cell Program (WCP))

and can be exported into excel for analysis. The microscopy images will be .tiff or .psd files that can be viewed and analysed with Adobe Photoshop or equivalent programs. The video files generated from the behavioural experiments will be in a standard video format .mp4.

The electrophysiological data sets collected from this project will be documented using experiment lists in Matlab that contain the parameters of each experiment in a standard way. These lists will be stored together with the Matlab code for analysis. These lists also allow to follow which data sets have been included in a particular analysis or which data sets had to be excluded.

4. ETHICS AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

How will ethical issues concerning data management (e.g. sensitive personal information, third-party access to data) be taken into account? Please note that the ethical issues that concern data collection and research implementation are described in the research plan.

My research project does not include any human data. Any ethical issues concern the care and use of animals as described in the research plan. Therefore there are no ethical issues regarding data management or access to the data.

How will copyright and IPR issues be managed?

The research project will not use any data which is covered by the Copyright, Designs and Patents or any other similar legislation. Every research partner will sign a contract agreeing that data arising from the research project will be made openly available where possible.

5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

How will the data be made available for subsequent use by other researchers?

Researchers will be able to contact the PI for access to the data. Due to the large size of the data files, this access will have to be organized on an individual basis, so that the relevant files can be downloaded upon request together with the metadata file (experiment list) for further information on the experiments.